

THE VIEWS OF EFL PREPARATORY STUDENTS ON THE USE OF MOBILE DEVICES IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

YABANCI DİL OLARAK İNGİLİZCE ÖĞRENEN HAZIRLIK ÖĞRENCİLERİNİN DİL ÖĞRENİMİNDE MOBİL CİHAZLARIN KULLANIMINA İLİŞKİN GÖRÜŞLERİ

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ABSTRACT

The use of technological devices in language education is a necessity because it is almost impossible to perform listening and speaking skills independently of technology. In this study, the answers of 25 students studying at the School of Foreign Languages in the 2021-2022 academic year at Van Yüzüncü Yıl University to a questionnaire which is prepared with Google Forms and contains five open-ended questions were analysed with the MAXQDA 2020 program. As a result of the analysis made, in line with the opinions of the preparatory students, it is concluded that the use of mobile devices in language education accelerates language learning and thus saves time, the learned information is more memorable, these devices are a significant source of resources, they make learning fun, they enable practice, and they enable ubiquitous learning. In addition, it has been understood that the students mostly use the *Tureng* dictionary which is from Turkish to English and English to Turkish in the classroom, followed by applications of *Cambridge* and *Oxford* dictionaries. Despite the fact that none of the students use a paper-based dictionary in the classroom, it is a surprising result of this study that nearly half of the participants state that the printed dictionary is more advantageous than the online dictionary. Furthermore, it was found that outside of classroom, students who are studying a foreign language spend the majority of their language-developing time using dictionary apps, followed by *YouTube*, *Cake*, and *Duolingo*.

Keywords: Mobile learning, mobile devices, Internet-based dictionary

ÖZET

Dil eğitiminde teknolojik cihazların kullanımı bir zorunluluktur çünkü dinleme ve konuşma becerilerini teknolojiden bağımsız olarak gerçekleştirmek neredeyse imkânsızdır. Bu çalışmada, Van Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi 2021-2022 Eğitim-Öğretim yılında Yabancı Diller Yüksekokulunda öğrenim gören 25 öğrencinin Google Formlar ile hazırlanan ve beş adet açık uçlu soru içeren ankete verdikleri cevaplar MAXQDA 2020 programı ile analiz edilmiştir. Yapılan analiz sonucunda, hazırlık öğrencilerinin görüşleri doğrultusunda, mobil cihazların dil eğitiminde kullanılması dil eğitimini hızlandırır ve dolayısıyla zamandan tasarruf sağlar, öğrenilen bilgiler daha akılda kalıcı olur, bu cihazların önemli bir kaynak deposudur, öğrenmeyi eğlenceli hale getirirler, pratik yapmayı sağlarlar ve her yerde öğrenmeyi mümkün kılarlar sonuçlarına ulaşmıştır. Ayrıca öğrencilerin sınıfta en çok Türkçeden İngilizceye ve İngilizceden Türkçeye olan *Tureng* sözlüğünü, ardından *Cambridge* ve *Oxford* sözlüklerinin uygulamalarını kullandıkları anlaşılmıştır. Öğrencilerin hiçbiri sınıfta

kâğıt tabanlı sözlük kullanmamasına rağmen yaklaşık yarısının basılı sözlüğün çevrimiçi sözlükten daha avantajlı olduğunu belirtmesi bu çalışmanın şaşırtıcı bir sonucudur. Ayrıca öğrencilerin, sınıf dışında dil gelişimleri için ayırdıkları zamanlarının büyük bir bölümünü, sözlük uygulamalarında geçirdikleri, bunu *YouTube*, *Cake* ve *Duolingo* uygulamalarının takip ettiği tespit edilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Mobil öğrenme, mobil cihazlar, internet tabanlı sözlük

INTRODUCTION

Beginning in the early 2000s, mobile devices swiftly gained popularity and expanded over the whole world. In a relatively short period of time, mobile gadgets like smartphones and tablets, which are widely utilized in daily life, have become an essential component of our lives. Although mobile devices have a wide range of capabilities, how each age group uses them varies. The capabilities and aspirations of the current generation are a little different from those of earlier generations since they are digital natives and were raised in a high-tech environment. Children are considerably more adept at using technology than their parents are, and they have higher expectations for the educational system as a whole. Instead of going to the library or buying a book, they opted to read whenever and wherever they wanted through their mobile devices. The fact that the younger generation is so intertwined with digital technology and uses it in every aspect of life necessitates a fundamental shift in the field of education.

Modern technology has developed rapidly and has affected education as well as every field. In the 1990s, computers were first used for educational purposes; today, tablets and phones have largely replaced computers. While computer-assisted language learning (CALL), which emerged due to the active use of computers in education, is still active, mobile-assisted language learning (MALL), an educational model that emerged with the use of mobile devices for educational purposes, is getting more popular day by day. However, there are some contradictions about allowing and providing mobile device usage for educational purposes. The majority of the academic community still forbids phones in the classroom and even on campuses, despite a rising number of educational institutions throughout the world embracing the use of mobile devices in their instructional modules (Irina, 2012). While some educators believe that mobile devices should be banned from conventional, structured learning environments, others believe that schools should adapt to the digital world. Students can individually learn a new language to a good level by downloading and benefiting from language-teaching applications, but the inclusion of mobile devices into formal education that teaches the language more academically and follows the rules will make face-to-face education much more enjoyable. Mobile devices can be adapted to the education system, as there are a large number of mobile device users, most of whom have multiple handsets.

Also, the fact that these devices have an internet connection makes them incredibly useful for learning languages because the internet has made it possible for everyone to easily access previously out-of-reach material. Thanks to mobile devices and the internet, anyone can read a book, view a video, or complete a quiz in a foreign language at any time. There are several ways that mobile phones may be used to study, such as blogs, e-books, electronic dictionaries, vocabulary games, surveys, podcasts, and short-form writing assignments. Even if they are not intentionally targeted, students' exposure to languages without restrictions on time or location allows for accidental acquisition (Irina 2012). Mobile devices enable students

to study or practice a foreign language almost anywhere, including cafes, airports, libraries, homes, and educational institutions.

Although a lot of study is being done in this area, the impact of mobile devices on education still raises some questions. This study explores the views of EFL preparatory class students about the use of mobile devices such as laptops, tablets, and phones in language learning.

Statement of the Problem

Portable devices such as laptops, phones, and tablets are widely used in all areas of our lives. Today, the number of phone users has reached 6.8 billion (Figure 3) and this shows that almost 86% of the world's population has at least one cell phone. Although mobile devices are widely used in all areas of life, they unfortunately lag behind in education. Even if they are used for educational purposes outside of the classroom, it is very rare for phones or tablets to be used in educational settings. One of the main reasons for this is that teachers are afraid of not being able to control the class because of the distractive features of phones. Aamri and Suleiman (2011) conducted research to observe the behaviours and attitudes of university students towards the use of mobile technologies in language learning in the classroom and found that, despite the fact that students enjoy learning with mobile devices; their use is constrained in formal settings due to teachers' disapproval. For studying languages, there are a ton of apps available on Google Play or the App Store and this feature of mobile devices can be used for language education. Although these contemporary tools may be really beneficial in educational environments, most regions of the world still do not permit their usage in the classroom. However, how useful smartphones can be in a controlled classroom environment is one of the main issues to be investigated in this field.

The use of mobile devices in formal education, both within and outside of the classroom, has been and will continue to be researched. These studies lead to discussions on the advantages and disadvantages of mobile devices in educational settings. Mobile devices are advantageously used in formal education in addition to being widely used for language learning outside of the classroom. According to a study by Wang et al., in-class vocabulary education for college students utilising an iPad app has been demonstrated to be much more successful (2015). Additionally, students can use a phone and it is crucial for SLA, according to Darni and Albion (2014), who examined past studies on the usage of mobile phones in formal educational settings. Many studies have shown that mobile devices are helpful in language learning and language teaching (Thornton and Houser, 2005; Saran and Seferolu, 2010; Alemi et al., 2012; Wang and Shih, 2015; Basoglu and Akdemir, 2010; Suwantarathip and Orawiatnakul, 2015), and learners are willing to take education with mobile devices (Mahat et al., 2012; Corbeil and Corbeil, 2011). Despite these and other research, it is still unknown whether or not employing mobile devices as a teaching tool in a formal education will benefit and be well-received by students. Cheon et al. (2012) noted that further research is necessary to confirm the impact of mobile device use on students and teachers.

Research Questions

1. What are EFL prep class students' views about the usage of mobile devices in language learning?

2. What are some of the most popular language-learning applications that EFL students use?

3. What are the opinions of EFL preparatory class students regarding the use of an online dictionary compared to a printed dictionary?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL)

Mobile devices like tablets and smartphones, which initially appeared in the 2000s, have quickly invaded every facet of life. It is predicted that they will fundamentally change the way that e-learning is done (Miangah and Nezarat, 2012). Prior to the development of mobile devices, technological tools were still employed as supplementary resources in the classroom, but mobile tools make learning more individualised and spontaneous. One may seek information and discover new things wherever and whenever they have a mobile device and an internet connection. It is no longer required to learn a language in a structured classroom setting; instead, people may locate online materials or online teachers from all over the world to study a language together. Mobile-assisted language learning (MALL), a novel language learning theory, has evolved as a result of the usage of mobile devices for language learning. The goal of mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) is to employ portable, lightweight devices like tablets and smartphones to study a language.

What Is Mobile Learning?

Mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) is defined by Kukulska-Hulme and Shield as "the use of personal, portable devices that enable new ways of learning, emphasizing continuity or spontaneity of access and interaction across different contexts of use," (2008, p. 273). Mobile learning, as defined by Traxler & Kukulska-Hulme, is the use of portable technologies like tablets, PDAs, and smartphones for learning within or outside of the classroom (2007). Some academics equate mobile learning with learning while on the road, even though the majority of researchers simply define it as learning with portable technological gadgets. According to O'Malley et al. (2003), mobile learning encompasses any sort of learning that takes place when the learner is on the go rather than being restricted to the portability of gadgets. These statements make it clear that even if there is not a clear definition of mobile learning, yet mobility plays a significant role in its justification.

Mohammed, Assam, and Saidi assert that with the use of mobile technology, all pupils may acquire an excellent education (2020). For the past 20 years, mobile learning has been embedded in several educational institutions all around the world. Mobile devices are perfect for usage in educational systems due of their mobility, customisation, and universality. Numerous nations have already adopted mobile technology into their educational institutions, including Qatar, Brazil, Thailand, South Korea, and the United Arab Emirates (Ally, 2013). High school pupils in Turkey were given tablets in 2015, enabling them to utilize them both inside and outside of the classroom. Despite the fact that mobile devices are being used in classrooms more often throughout the world, some educators are hesitant to employ them in formal education because they worry that doing so would interfere with the learning environment. Instructors frequently believe that learning may occur in courses that are structured and controlled. In light of the fact that it is difficult to stop the younger generation from using their phones, educators should reconsider their stance and be ready for a classroom that is technologically updated and allows students to utilize their personal mobile devices.

It is essential that technology tools be used in educational settings. As long as we are aware of the disruption they will make to conventional teaching techniques and know how to

handle it, we may tolerate kids who enter the classroom with smartphones and laptops. This does not support the notion that since children have access to new technology, education must adapt to meet their needs. The ability technology-enhanced learning is more reasonable. The ability to create and explore information, interact with and work with peers, and control one's learning are basic components of effective learning (Sharples, 2002).

Mobile learning stands out for three reasons: it is personalized, pervasive, and ubiquitous (Sharples, 2002). As practically everyone owns a personal mobile device, the individual may control his or her own education without assistance from a superior; in other words, the person can study independently without the aid of a teacher or an expert. Also, since mobile devices are accessible to virtually every section of society, no one is deprived of accessing to education. Everyone can conduct an online search on a topic they are interested in and quickly find the knowledge they need. Mobile learning is also available everywhere; it doesn't require a set schedule and may occur whenever and wherever it's convenient. Every time a person connects to the internet, there is a possibility to learn something new, and owing to mobile devices, learning is now possible anytime, anywhere, and outside of a structured learning setting.

As a result, learning is a continuous process that lasts for the whole of one's life. Together with formal education in the classroom, informal education frequently occurs outside of it with no time restrictions. With the development of technology, particularly the creation of mobile devices, most learning now occurs when a person is on the move. Mobile devices allow for personalized and portable learning, but those who have a learning intent need to have strong self-authority and will because there are thousands of apps available on the App Store and Google Play Store that aren't all for educational purposes; there are even more apps that are designed for entertainment. The student must develop self-control to spend time using educational applications because no one is in charge of controlling the learners and there are several diversions on these gadgets. Yet, blended mobile learning can help students in learning environments when mobile devices are used in formal education since the teacher will also support the student in self-control.

Mobile devices

People utilize mobile devices, including laptops, smartphones, tablets, personal digital assistants (PDAs), and other portable technology, for a range of activities, including communication, information collecting, entertainment, and so on. There are many different types of mobile devices, and Figure 1 shows the mobile devices that are used the most frequently.

Figure 1. Kinds of the most commonly used mobile devices

Users may select the mobile devices that best fit their needs and budget because they are available in a wide range of sizes and forms (Figure 2). The sole complaint about mobile devices was their tiny screens (Stockwell, 2010), yet this complaint is no longer applicable due to advancements in technology.

Figure 2. The evolution of the mobile phone

Mobile devices work because of their operating systems, which are the most important piece of software since they manage all other software and hardware. The two most popular operating systems are Android, developed by Google, and iOS, produced by Apple Inc. According to Statista, iOS has a market share of 24% compared to 75% for Android (2020). 5.28 billion people use mobile devices worldwide as of today, accounting for 67.95% of the global population (bankmycell, 2020). With 3.5 billion smartphones being used worldwide in 2020, smartphones account for the largest portion of those mobile devices (Statista, 2020). These figures are predicted to rise as a result of the strong allure of mobile devices. Nearly

everyone will have a mobile device in a relatively short period, and some people will have more than one. The number of mobile devices worldwide is increasing, as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Forecast number of mobile devices worldwide from 2023 to 2027 (Statista, 2023)

Important Features of Mobile Devices

Portability: Mobile devices include a lot of functions. Their lightness, portability, and tiny size are their most impressive features. These are quite simple to carry with you wherever you go. Mobile devices are lighter than laptops, thus one may carry them in a backpack or pocket for a longer period of time. The most intriguing feature of mobile devices is that, in addition to having a wide variety of applications, you can take them wherever you go. Learners may obtain information anywhere they desire by being portable and having access to the internet everywhere. No matter where they are—at home, at school, on the bus, in the hospital—those who want to learn a new language may access movies, read passages, listen to podcasts, and complete vocabulary-building exercises.

A rich source of materials: Mobile devices are very appealing to educators when used in conjunction with the internet since they provide access to a variety of instructional resources (Traxler & Kukulska-Hulme, 2007). Mobile technologies allow enormous access to a vast range of materials, personalize and spread instruction, and boost students' success (Power, 2019). A learner now has access to a variety of educational apps on the Google Play and App stores, as well as a large selection of educational reading materials, films, and videos. This feature of mobile devices can significantly enhance learners' linguistic abilities, for instance, a mobile device is an important resource for listening skills since it offers hundreds of movies, music, and podcasts in the target language. Another fantastic aspect of mobile devices is the ability to support communication in other languages. Most notably, a fantastic feature of these programs is the inclusions of thousands of reading texts in the target language that promote vocabulary and grammatical development.

Usability: One of the defining variables for a successful teaching and learning process is a device's usability. When a tool is useful, it indicates that using it is not difficult. These days, mobile gadgets are so simple to use that even young children can use them. Usable

electronics are typically seen as being straightforward to use, efficient, competent, and enjoyable from the user's perspective, according to Kukulska-Hulme (2005). Producers should concentrate on a variety of factors, such as the psychology of customers as well as the cost and usefulness of the item, in order to design user-friendly gadgets. From a pedagogical standpoint, a gadget must offer qualified engagement and a suitable learning opportunity in order to be useful.

Affordability: Even while some mobile devices are fairly pricey, they are typically priced to fit a range of budgets. Anybody may choose a mobile device that fits their budget because costs and sizes of mobile devices vary. Being affordable makes mobile devices available to all facets of society, enabling learning to take place outside of the classroom as well.

Functions of Mobile Devices

The current mobile device provides a wide range of possibilities, including online surfing, picture and video taking, geo-location services, and more (Bohmer et al., 2011). They may therefore be used for more than just sending and receiving messages and making phone calls, making them more than "just cellphones" (Bouca, 2012). Mobile devices make it simple to conduct all of the computer-related activities-checking emails, listening to music, viewing videos, and conducting Internet searches-without any time or location restrictions. With its many features, you may send or receive money when you need to, play games when you're bored, study a topic, take pictures of a beautiful scene, and avoid getting lost. The functions of mobile devices are displayed in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The functions of mobile devices (Trinder, 2007).

Organization, communication, relaxation, information, and application are the five key categories under which Trinder (2004) categorized the uses of cell phones. What can be done with these portable and personal computers is shown in Figure 5. While there have been a few minor changes since he formed these classifications in 2004, the most of what can be done with mobile devices remains the same. They enable audio and video recording and sharing in addition to offering instant communication and teamwork. These portable media players let you watch videos and listen to music. They resemble little televisions. They also serve as a library, offering a variety of books and articles for reading. Mobile devices also come with a variety of games that may be both educational and entertaining.

Figure 5. Categories of reasons of mobile device usage

METHODOLOGY

Design and Process of the Study

This study is a case study, which is one of the qualitative research methods, and the effect of using mobile devices in language education in or out of the classroom of students learning English as a foreign language on language education is investigated.

Participants and Process of the Study

Preparatory students at Van Yüzüncü Yıl University in the 2021–2022 academic year. These students are between the ages of 17-22 and get English education 24 hours a week. As a resource, they utilise New English File Series which have an online application and online practice activities. During the lessons, the teachers open the applications of the books they use as a resource from the Oxford publications on their laptop computers and teach the lesson

with this application. In addition, students can access the online practice section of the New English File book from their phones and do the online practice activities. Additionally, students are allowed to use their phones to learn the meanings and pronunciations of unfamiliar words, so they do not carry paper-based dictionaries with them.

Figure 6. Demographic distribution of the participants

Data Collection and Data Analysis

A questionnaire consisting of five open-ended questions was administered to the students, and 25 of 40 students voluntarily fill in this questionnaire. The answers given were analysed with MAXQDA 2020 and thematic concepts were created. The validity of the questionnaire is determined because it was reviewed by three experts.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

RQ.1. What are EFL prep class students' views about the usage of mobile devices in language learning?

More than 30 percent of preparatory class students think that language learning is faster and time-saving thanks to mobile devices, and 26,1 percent say that information is more memorable thanks to mobile devices. While 21,7 percent of the students state that the number of mobile resources is high, nearly 9 percent of them argue that language education with mobile devices is more fun. 6.5 percent of the participants argue that mobile devices make it possible to practice, and 6.5 percent claim that learning through mobile devices is ubiquitous, that is, it takes place without restrictions of place and time. There are many positive comments like “with visual and auditory technology, learning a foreign language becomes easier and more fun”(P7) or “since learning a language requires practice, we can improve our language by watching movies, TV series, lecture videos, etc., thanks to technological devices (P12). As a result of the positive comments made by the students, it can be deduced that mobile devices are quite effective in language education.

EFL Students' Views about the Usage of Mobile Devices in Language Learning

Figure 7. Students' views about mobile device usage in language learning

RQ.2. What are some of the most popular language-learning applications that EFL students use?

The researcher asked two open-ended questions corresponding to second research question in the questionnaire. As stated before, as instructors of School of Foreign Languages in Van Yüzüncü Yıl University, we allow our preparatory students to use their phones for online dictionary usage in the classroom. In one of the open-ended question, the researcher asked the students about the dictionary application they use most in the classroom. Although the usage rates are close to each other, It is seen that many students use the Tureng dictionary from Turkish to English and English to Turkish (40%), followed by Cambridge (33,3%) and Oxford (26,7%) dictionaries, respectively.

The Most Commonly Used Applications (in the classroom)

Figure 8. The dictionary that students use in class

In another open-ended question, students were asked about the applications they use most often outside of the classroom for language learning, and when the answers were

analysed, the following graphic came up. More than half of the students spend time on various dictionary applications to improve their target language, followed by *Cake*, *Duolingo* and *YouTube* at the same rate. Also, some of the students use *Voice of America* and *Ted Talks* applications for language development.

Figure 9. Most commonly used applications outside of the class.

RQ.3. What are the opinions of EFL preparatory class students regarding the use of an online dictionary compared to a printed dictionary

All of the students look quickly on the phone when they need to look up a word in the lesson, and many students say that internet-based dictionary saves time and it is very fast to reach the word. There are no students who bring a printed dictionary to the classroom, but there are students who say that looking up a word from an internet-based dictionary is not memorable, provides limited learning, is distracting, and pushes people into laziness.

In internet-based dictionary usage, we focus on a single word, but in paper-based dictionary usage, when one word is looked at, another word may attract attention. In paper-based dictionaries, you can take your hand and learn new words every day. However, in digital dictionaries, we look up the words that we are stuck or curious about at that moment. In this way, it slows us down and destroys the investigative spirit. (P21)

This study acknowledges that students' opinions on using online dictionaries in the classroom vary widely. Also, when comparing online and printed dictionaries, students' opinions diverge, demonstrating the need for further research in this area. As a result of the analysis of the answers given by the students to the open-ended question, the thematic table showing the advantages and disadvantages of using the online dictionary was created and provided below.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Using a Dictionary Application Instead of a Printed Dictionary in Class

	Themes	Explanations	Participants' Comments
Advantages of Online Dictionary	Fast and Time-Saving (17)	Most of the students say that searching for words in the online dictionary is very fast and this saves a lot of time.	<p><i>-Having immediate access to the word you are looking up is a very good thing. Wasting time searching through a paper-based dictionary keeps impatient people away from learning. (P25)</i></p> <p><i>-Using an internet-based dictionary in the classroom saves more time in finding the searched word than a paper-based dictionary, and the searched word can be found instantly. (P15)</i></p> <p><i>-We can get results in a shorter time and we can get results even in more complex searches. (P23)</i></p>
	Getting more Information about the Word (7)	Students state that when they look up word via online dictionary, they can also listen to the pronunciation of the word, easily reach the synonyms and antonyms of the word, and encounter many example sentences in which the word is used.	<p><i>-Our speed of finding the word we are looking for increases, we can reach all the information about the word more easily. (P1)</i></p> <p><i>-We don't waste too much time and we learn synonyms or different meanings of a word. (P3)</i></p> <p><i>-As a positive aspect, the pronunciation of the word we are looking for is more understandable than the internet-based dictionary and we can easily access it. (P20)</i></p>
Disadvantages of Online Dictionary	Not Memorable (6)	Some students say that they quickly forget the words they look up in the online dictionary, but the words they search in the printed dictionary are more memorable.	<p><i>-I think it is not memorable to look up words in the online dictionary. While I still remember a word I looked up from the printed dictionary years ago, I can't remember a word I looked up on the internet this morning. (P11)</i></p> <p><i>-I believe that the internet-based dictionary has a faster, more useful, but more frequently forgotten usage, whereas the paper-based dictionary is slower but more memorable. (P5)</i></p>
	Limited Learning (6)	Students state that when they look up words from the printed dictionary, they also learn many other words together, but this is not possible in the online dictionary.	<p><i>-We can learn different words while searching for a word in paper-based dictionaries, but this is not the case in internet-based dictionaries (P10)</i></p> <p><i>-The paper-based dictionary is a waste of time, but it also provides familiarity with many words until you find the searched word.(P2)</i></p>
	Being Distracting (2)	A small number of students state that they get distracted and look at other applications while using a dictionary application.	<i>-Being fast is the most obvious aspect of the internet-based dictionary, but it can also be very distracting. (P2)</i>
	Causing Laziness (2)	Considering how simple it is to look up words in an online dictionary, a tiny percentage of students claim that this causes students to be lazy.	<i>-Internet-based dictionary is easier to access and word search, but it makes one lazier which has negative effects in the long run, for example, poor research ability because no one wants to waste time when there is easy access (from unreliable sources). (P18)</i>

CONCLUSION

It is almost impossible to execute some language learning skills like speaking and listening without the aid of technology, thus the use of technological tools in language instruction is a requirement. According to the findings of the analysis and the opinions of the preparatory students, it can be said that the use of mobile devices in language education speeds up language learning and thus saves time. Some other results of the study are that it makes the information learned more memorable, these devices are a significant source of resources, learning is made fun, practise is made possible, and ubiquitous learning is made possible. Also, it is noted that in the classroom, students mostly utilise the *Tureng* dictionary, which is available in both Turkish and English, followed by the *Cambridge* and *Oxford* dictionaries. It is a remarkable finding of this study that, despite the fact that none of the students utilise a paper-based dictionary in the classroom, over half of them believe that the printed dictionary is preferable to the online dictionary. Further, it was shown that students who are learning a foreign language outside of the classroom spend the bulk of their time utilising dictionary applications, followed by *YouTube*, *Cake*, and *Duolingo*.

As a result, it is an undeniable fact that mobile devices contribute significantly to language education. Even if the educators think that the use of mobile devices in the classroom is distracting and uncontrollable, it would be appropriate to implement at least some of the extracurricular activities using mobile devices, because the new generation are glued to these devices, so their beneficial use and use for language education should be provided.

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